

Influence of Depression and anxiety as predictors of substance use among youths in keffi local Government area, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined depression and anxiety as predictors of substance use among youths in Keffi Local Government Area, Nasarawa State-Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design approach, which did not allow for manipulation of the study variables, and of course simple random sampling technique was used to select, one hundred and fourty-three (143) participants of male female were selected. In addition to providing demographic data, participants responded to (3) standardized self-report questionnaires. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. On the whole, three hypotheses were formulated and inferentially tested at 0.05 level of significant, using simple linear regression analysis, and independent sample t-test. Results from analysis indicates as follows: hypothesis one tested that depression has a significant determinant on substance use among youths in Keffi local Government Area [$\beta = .427, t = 4.670; p < .001$] significantly and positively accepted. Hypothesis two also stated that anxiety will have a significant determinant on substance use among youth Keffi Local Government Area [$\beta = -.497; t = -5.676; p < .001$] was therefore accepted. Based on the findings, the study recommended as follows: that future researcher should explore the neurobiological underpinnings that link depression, anxiety, and addiction, such as alterations in brain regions involved in reward processing and emotional regulation, Assess the effectiveness of integrated treatment approaches that simultaneously address both mental health disorders and substance abuse, evaluating therapeutic outcomes like relapse prevention and long-term recovery.

Keywords: depression, anxiety and substance use

Introduction

Substance use has been a source of persistent concern for parents, educators, and lawmakers given that it has been generally linked to poor adult outcomes (Kuropka et al., 2023). Despite the recent decline in the proportion of youth reporting use of certain licit and illicit substances,

substance use among the youths remains relatively pervasive. According to the recent national survey of youths, *Monitoring the Future* (2019), use of some illicit drugs such as crystal methamphetamine, crack, and cocaine has gradually declined in the past ten years (Jensen et al., 2020). Several students experience mental health problem, either temporarily the increase of substance use globally has brought problems such as increase in violence, crimes and diseases like HIV/AIDS, collapse of the veins and collapse in the social structure of the society, (Oshodi,2019). Substance use threatens the security of every nation, tearing apart the societies, spawning crime, spreading diseases such as AIDS, destroying youths and the future of the country. On the other hand, anxiety as natural human emotion, encompasses various behavioural, emotional, and cognitive reactions that occur when an individual perceives a sense of danger (Muller, 2014). However, anxiety becomes problematic when it exceeds normal levels and leads to substantial distress or interference in daily functioning (Windarwati et al., 2022). Most times, youths do not know when this may create a heightened sense of uncertainty and hopelessness about the future leading to increased levels of anxiety.

When faced with excessive demands that become overwhelming, depression emerges as a result. Depression occurs when an individual's ability to handle these demands surpasses their coping mechanisms, leading to a range of serious health risks (Oduwaiye et al., 2017). In other words, depression arises when the challenges of work or life become too much for a person to manage, posing significant threats to their well-being. These experiences include loss of sense of belonging, difficulties adjusting to new surroundings, financial strain due to loss of sense of income, abuse, the struggle for basic amenities such as clean water, shelter, food, sanitation facilities and health care (Ajibade et al., 2017). Therefore, this study aims on investigating depression and anxiety as a determinant of substance use among youths in keffi local government, it will also examine the causes and effects of substance use and will set proactive measures to which may enable youths to desist from using it.

Statement of the Problem

Substance use is not a strange phenomenon, rather a global regional and national dimension as documented. The physical, psychological, social and economic consequences of the drug problems among youths are becoming more apparent, worrisome and disturbing. In particular, drug use among youth in Keffi has been on the rise in recent years, with anti-narcotics officials and experts warning of serious social consequences if the problem is not addressed (NDLEA,

2021). One of the most delicate phases is the youth period and in many cases at this stage, the initiating of drug use may occur. Youth may abuse substances due to various reasons such as lack of adequate knowledge about the harmful effects of the substances, presenting personal independence, peer pressure, satisfying the curiosity, low levels of self-confidence, inability in maintaining inter-personal communications. A number of factors are consistently found to be related to substance use among youth including the community, school environment, peer, family and personal factors (Brook et al., 2008). Some common reasons for substance use include distance from school, lack of social support from the parent or caregivers, psychological and emotional neglect (Grobler & Khatite, 2012; Ward, 2007; Westling, et al., 2008). Beyond this, broader economic difficulties experienced by communities due to scarce resources and lack of leisure activities are further associated with problematic behaviours (Godbey 2009; Wegner et al., 2008).

Research Questions

The study answered following research questions:

- i. What is the predictor of depression on substance use among Youths in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State-Nigeria?
- ii. What is the predictor of anxiety on Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State-Nigeria

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated for this study.

- i. Depression will serve as a significant predictor of substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State.
- ii. Anxiety will serve as a significant predictor of Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant for several reasons, as it contributes to both theoretical knowledge and practical interventions in addressing Research on depression, anxiety on substance use is relevant in several ways including: Identifying the determinant of depression, anxiety, on substance use levels among Youth in Keffi Local Government Area, Nasarawa State, and the findings of this study will contribute towards providing evidence-based recommendations that can be used by organizations and mental health practitioners involved in the provision of support

services for Youth. The intersection of depression, anxiety, and substance use disorders represents a significant public health concern. The high prevalence of comorbidity, coupled with the complex interplay between these conditions, necessitates comprehensive and integrated treatment approaches. Ongoing research is critical to further understanding the underlying mechanisms and developing more effective interventions to improve outcomes for individuals with these co-occurring disorders.

Scope of the Study

The study on depression and anxiety as a predictor of substance use will cover the youths who are receiving treatment and rehabilitation on drug related problems at rehabilitation center in designated Keffi, Nasarawa State. The study shall also proffer professional suggestions on controls measures to ensure that substance use is reduced to the lowest minimum. This research will be a survey study where questionnaire will be used for the collection of data and the study will be restricted only to the youth in Keffi, Nasarawa

Conceptual Clarification/Literature review

This section presents the conceptual definitions of key variables in the study and critically reviews related empirical literature to provide a theoretical and research-based foundation for understanding the depression, anxiety, on substance use levels among Youth in Keffi Local Government Area, Nasarawa State

Depression and Substance Abuse

In 2018, Adole conducted a study titled "Prevalence and Correlates of Substance Abuse among Secondary School Students in Kogi State". The researchers used the Self-Medication Hypothesis as their guiding theory. They conducted a cross-sectional survey among 500 secondary school students. The findings revealed a high prevalence of substance abuse (34.5%), with a significant association between substance abuse and symptoms of anxiety and depression. The authors concluded that anxiety and depression were significant determinants of substance abuse among youths in Kogi.

In 2019, Yusuf conducted a study titled "Socioeconomic Factors and Substance Abuse among Youths with Mental Health Issues in Keffi LGA". The Social Disorganization Theory was employed in this research. The study was conducted over two years, involving a cohort of 300 youths. The findings indicated that youths from lower socioeconomic backgrounds were more likely to resort to substance abuse when dealing with anxiety and depression. The authors

highlighted the importance of addressing socioeconomic disparities in interventions aimed at reducing substance abuse.

A more recent study was conducted by Abdullahi et al., in 2021, titled "Effectiveness of Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy in Reducing Substance Abuse and Mental Health Symptoms among Youths in Lafia LGA" uses The Cognitive-Behavioral Theory in conducting the research. The researchers conducted a randomized controlled trial, involving 100 youths who received CBT and a control group of 100 youths who did not. The study found that CBT was effective in reducing both substance abuse and symptoms of anxiety and depression. The authors recommended the implementation of CBT in intervention programs for youths in Lafia LGA. In 2017, a study by Muhammad et al. titled "Mental Health Issues and Substance Abuse among Adolescents in Kano LGA" explored the prevalence of mental health issues and substance abuse in this population. The study used the Stress Process Model as its theoretical framework. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 400 adolescents. The findings revealed a high prevalence of both mental health issues (anxiety and depression) and substance abuse. The authors concluded that there was a significant association between mental health issues and substance abuse, suggesting that anxiety and depression could be determinants of substance abuse.

Anxiety and Substance use

De Berardis et al., (2008) investigated an increasing body of studies indicating that alexithymia features exist not only in classic psychosomatic disorders but also in other severe and chronic somatic diseases and psychiatric disorders such as Major Depression, and other Axis I disorders such as anxiety disorders. The authors tried to elucidate the relationships between alexithymia and anxiety disorders, in order to investigate possible psychopathological and therapeutic implications.

Another study of Ames and Roitzsch (2012), patients who endorsed a greater overall number of daily anxiety, had a higher probability of experiencing cravings. The authors propose two possible hypotheses for this finding. First, individuals who experience a greater number of anxiety may experience cravings because substance use has been associated with anxiety minor life events since these individuals have used substances as a means of coping with these events in the past. This hypothesis is consistent with the tension reduction theory of substance use as proposed by Cappell and Greeley (1987). Second, an alternative hypothesis is that individuals who report experiencing a greater

number of minor anxiety may also experience cravings because they have a heightened attention to these anxiety events, thereby influencing the number of cravings they experience.

Cummings et al., (2014) addressed descriptive and developmental factors, gender differences, suicidality, assessments, and treatment-outcome research as they relate to comorbid anxiety and depression, and to their three pathways. Research indicated that comorbidity varies depending on the specific anxiety disorder: Pathway 1 describes youth with either social phobia or separation anxiety disorder and subsequent depression, Pathway 2 applies to youth with co-primary generalised anxiety disorder and depression, and Pathway 3 includes depressed youth with subsequent social phobia. Dobrean and Păsărelu (2016) conducted comprehensive systematic searches of electronic databases (PsychInfo, Cochrane, PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science) combining terms related to online social networking with social anxiety terms, and found that only recently researchers have started to investigate their relationship with mental health.

Methodology

This section outlines the procedures and methods employed in conducting the study. It explains the research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, instruments used for data collection, methods of data collection, validity and reliability of the instruments, as well as the statistical techniques used for data analysis. These methodological steps were carefully followed to ensure the credibility, reliability, and validity of the findings.

Research Design

This study adopted a survey research design, which was deemed appropriate as it enables the collection of data from a large group of respondents using standardized questionnaires. The design facilitated the examination of depression and anxiety on substance use among Youths in Keffi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State Nigeria. The survey design was suitable because the researchers sought to describe existing conditions without manipulating the variables under investigation. In this study, the independent variables social support and demographic characteristic, while depression serves as the dependent variable.

Population Sample And Sampling Technique

The population of the study comprised both male and female youths aged 18-35 years resident in Keffi for the period of study. Following the total population of three hundred and six (306)

youth as registered as confirmed by the researcher in the Keffi Youth center; the sample for this study, the researcher used Raosoft sample size calculator to determine the sample of participants used out of the total population of 306 youth. The sample size calculator gives a determined sample size of 143 participants that were used for the study; this means 143 measurements/surveys were used for a confidence level of 95% that the real value is within $\pm 5\%$ of the measured/surveyed value using the formula:

Unlimited population:

$$CI = \hat{p} \pm z \times \sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{n}}$$

Finite population:

$$CI' = \hat{p} \pm z \times \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n'} \times \frac{N-n'}{N-1}}$$

Where:

z is z score = 306

\hat{p} is the population proportion = 0.05

n and **n'** are sample size = .5

N is the population size = 143

Therefore, 143 participants was selected to participate in the study. This figure constituted the research study sample.

Research Instrument

Section: A: Beck Depression Inventory – II. The Beck Depression Inventory – II is a 21 item self-report instrument developed by Beck et al., (1996). It assesses the existence and severity of symptoms of depression. It is designed for individuals aged 13 and above. Each of the 21 items corresponding to a symptom of depression is summed to give a single score for the BDI – II. Total score of 0 -13 is considered minimal depression, 14 – 19 is mild depression, 20 – 28 is moderate, and 29 – 63 is severe depression. BDI – II is positively correlated with the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale with a Pearson r of 0.71, showing good agreement. The test has a high one-week test-retest reliability (Pearson r = 0.93), suggesting that it was not overly sensitive to daily variations in mood (Beck et al., 1996). The test also has high internal consistency ($\alpha = .91$) (Beck et al., 1996). **Section: B Self-Rated Anxiety Scale (SAS)** developed by Zung (1971), The SAS is a 20 item self-report tool designed for measuring the level of anxiety in an individual based on the common symptoms of anxiety. Fifteen of the items express negative experience

(e.g. I feel afraid for no reason at all) while five items express positive experience (e.g. I can breathe in and out easily). To respond to the items, an individual is required to indicate how much each statement applies to him/her within one or two weeks before taking the test. The SAS is measured on a Likert scale of 1- 4 which are: "a little of the time", "some of the time", "a good part of the time" and "most of the time". The items which express positive experience are scored in reverse. After scoring, the items are summed up to provide the total raw score which range from 20 - 80. The total raw score is then converted into an "Anxiety Index" Higher scores reflect a higher level of anxiety. The conversion and interpretation of the total raw score to anxiety index is given below:

For the original scale, Zung (1971) reported an internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.74 among a sample of psychiatric and non-psychiatric patients while Ramirez and Lukenbill (2008) reported an internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.80 for the SAS among a sample of adults and caregivers. For the current study, a pilot study was conducted using a sample of 40 young adults in the Keffi local government Council, Nasarawa state, to ascertain the reliability of the SAS for the study's target population. An alpha reliability coefficient of 0.69 was obtained indicating that the SAS is reliable for use in the current study. Section: C Substance Use, using the DAST which was modeled after the widely used Michigan Alcoholism Screening Test and was developed by (Selzer, 1971). Measurement properties of the DAST were initially evaluated using a clinical sample of 256 drug-alcohol-abuse clients (Skinner, 1982). The 20-item DAST has excellent internal consistency reliability (alpha) at 0.95 for total sample and 0.86 for the drug-abuse sample. Good discrimination is evident among clients classified by their reason for seeking treatment. Most clients with alcohol-related problems scored 5 or below, whereas the majority of clients with drug problems scored 6 or above on the 20-item DAST. The DAST-10 correlates very highly ($r = 0.98$) with the longer DAST-20 and has high internal consistency reliability for a brief scale (0.92 for the total sample and 0.74 for the drug-abuse sample).

Technique for Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the demographic characteristics and general responses of participants, while inferential statistics such as multiple regression and simple linear regression were used to test the research hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

This hypothesis stated that depression would have a significant predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. This hypothesis was tested using simple linear regression and the result is presented in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Summary of simple linear regression analysis showing the predictor of depression on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State

DV	Predictors	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	p
Substance Abuse	Constant	.427	.182	21.811	1, 142			
	Depression					.427	4.670	<.001

Table 4.2 shows the predictor of depression on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result shows that depression will have a significant predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State [$R = .427$ and $R^2 = .182$; $F(1, 142) = 21.811$; $p < .001$]. The result further shows through coefficient of determination [$R^2 = .182$] that depression significantly accounted for 18.2% of the total variance observed in substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result further shows through the observation of beta weight [$\beta = .427$, $t = 4.670$; $p < .001$] that depression positively predict substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. Based on this result, hypothesis one which stated that ‘depression will have a significant predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State’ was therefore accepted

Hypothesis Two

This hypothesis stated that anxiety would have a significant predictor on Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. This hypothesis was tested using simple linear regression and the result is presented in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Summary of simple linear regression analysis showing the predictor of anxiety on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State

DV	Predictors	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	p
Substance Abuse	Constant	.497	.247	32.215	1, 142			

Anxiety	.497	5.676	<.001
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Table 4.3 shows the predictor of anxiety on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result shows that anxiety significantly predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State [$R = .497$ and $R^2 = .247$; $F(1, 142) = 5.676$; $p < .001$]. The result further shows through coefficient of determination [$R^2 = .247$] that anxiety significantly accounted for 24.7% of the total variance observed in substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result further shows through the observation of beta weight [$\beta = .497$, $t = 5.676$; $p < .001$] that anxiety positively predict substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. Based on this result, hypothesis two which stated that ‘anxiety will have a significant predictor on Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State’ was therefore accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that depression significantly predicts substance use among youths in Keffi Local Government, accounting for 18.2% of the variance in substance use behaviors. This result aligns with the study by Adole et al., (2018), which reported a significant relationship between depression and substance abuse among secondary school students in Kogi State. Similarly, Abdullahi et al., (2021) highlighted the effectiveness of interventions like CBT in addressing both depression and substance use, underscoring the interrelation between the two. These findings support Beck’s Cognitive Theory, which posits that maladaptive schemas and negative automatic thoughts associated with depression can predispose individuals to maladaptive coping strategies, including substance use. The findings suggest the need for mental health interventions focused on early identification and treatment of depression among youths to reduce substance use. Integrating mental health services with substance use treatment programs can create a more comprehensive support system for vulnerable youths.

The results of the second also showed that anxiety significantly predicts substance use, explaining 24.7% of the variance. This corroborates the findings of Ames and Roitzsch (2012), who observed that anxiety significantly increases cravings for substances as a coping mechanism, consistent with the tension reduction theory. Furthermore, the work of De Berardis et al., (2008) underscores the overlap between anxiety disorders and substance use, suggesting

that the physiological arousal associated with anxiety often drives self-medication behaviors. These results align with Freud's Psychoanalytic Theory, which postulates that anxiety acts as a defense mechanism, potentially leading to maladaptive behaviors such as substance use to manage unconscious conflicts. The significant role of anxiety in substance use underscores the importance of anxiety management in prevention and treatment strategies. Programs designed to teach stress-reduction techniques, such as mindfulness or cognitive-behavioral approaches, could effectively reduce substance use by addressing anxiety triggers.

Lastly, the study found a significant gender difference in substance use, with females reporting higher mean scores compared to males. This finding contrasts with earlier studies such as those by Kandel et al., (1978) and Wilsnack et al., (1984), which identified males as more likely to engage in substance use. However, the results align with more recent research by Greenfield et al., (2010), which suggests that females may experience more severe consequences from substance use and are more likely to use substances as a response to psychological distress. The Gender and Trauma Theory by Pedersen et al., (2017) may provide insight, highlighting how societal pressures and trauma differently influence substance use patterns across genders. These findings indicate the need for gender-specific interventions in addressing substance use. Female-targeted programs should consider addressing underlying psychological distress and societal pressures, while male-focused interventions might emphasize peer influence and social norms. Tailored interventions can enhance the effectiveness of prevention and treatment strategies.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there is a significant association between symptoms of depression , anxiety and substance use among youths in Keffi LGA. This relationship is often reciprocal, with psychological distress potentially leading to substance use as a maladaptive coping mechanism (self-medication), and substance use, in turn, exacerbating mental health symptoms. A substantial number of youths engaging in substance use also exhibit elevated levels of depression and anxiety, highlighting a critical issue of co-occurring mental health and substance use disorders (dual diagnosis).Risk Factors: Factors such as peer pressure and male gender were also likely identified as significant predictors of substance use, consistent with regional findings, which may further complicate the mental health-substance use link.

Recommendations

The study's findings necessitate a multi-level approach involving clinical, educational, and community interventions.

- i. Integrated Treatment Services: Clinical psychology services (mental health and substance use) should be integrated, shifting away from treating these conditions in isolation.
- ii. School-Based Mental Health Programs: Implement Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)-based counseling and psycho-education programs in secondary schools and tertiary institutions within Keffi LGA. These programs should aim to teach youths:
- iii. Community and Family Intervention: Public health campaigns should target parents and community leaders to raise awareness about the signs of depression, anxiety, and substance use in youths.

Implications for Clinical Psychology

The study's results have several significant implications for the practice and development of clinical psychology services in Keffi and similar settings in Nigeria.

- i. Focus on Assessment and Early Detection: Clinicians must routinely screen all youth presenting with substance use problems for co-occurring depression and anxiety, and vice-versa, to ensure comprehensive diagnosis. This requires using culturally sensitive and validated assessment tools.
- ii. Specialized Training: There is an urgent need for mental health professionals to receive specialized training in co-morbidity treatment models like Motivational Interviewing (MI) and integrated CBT for substance use and anxiety/depression.
- ii. Advocacy and Policy: The findings provide empirical evidence to advocate for increased funding and resource allocation from the Keffi LGA and Nasarawa State government for youth mental health and substance abuse services, including the deployment of more career masters and psychologists in schools, as current efforts may be insufficient.

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Introduction

Substance use has been a source of persistent concern for parents, educators, and lawmakers given that it has been generally linked to poor adult outcomes (Kuropka et al., 2023). Despite the recent decline in the proportion of youth reporting use of certain licit and illicit substances, substance use among the youths remains relatively pervasive. According to the recent national survey of youths, *Monitoring the Future* (2019), use of some illicit drugs such as crystal methamphetamine, crack, and cocaine has gradually declined in the past ten years (Jensen et al., 2020). Several students experience mental health problem, either temporarily the increase of substance use globally has brought problems such as increase in violence, crimes and diseases like HIV/AIDS, collapse of the veins and collapse in the social structure of the society, (Oshodi,2019). Substance use threatens the security of every nation, tearing apart the societies, spawning crime, spreading diseases such as AIDS, destroying youths and the future of the country. On the other hand, anxiety as natural human emotion, encompasses various behavioural, emotional, and cognitive reactions that occur when an individual perceives a sense of danger (Muller, 2014). However, anxiety becomes problematic when it exceeds normal levels and leads to substantial distress or interference in daily functioning

(Windarwati et al., 2022). Most times, youths do not know when this may create a heightened sense of uncertainty and hopelessness about the future leading to increased levels of anxiety.

When faced with excessive demands that become overwhelming, depression emerges as a result. Depression occurs when an individual's ability to handle these demands surpasses their coping mechanisms, leading to a range of serious health risks (Oduwaiye et al., 2017). In other words, depression arises when the challenges of work or life become too much for a person to manage, posing significant threats to their well-being. These experiences include loss of sense of belonging, difficulties adjusting to new surroundings, financial strain due to loss of sense of income, abuse, the struggle for basic amenities such as clean water, shelter, food, sanitation facilities and health care (Ajibade et al., 2017). Therefore, this study aims on investigating depression and anxiety as a determinant of substance use among youths in keffi local government, it will also examine the causes and effects of substance use and will set proactive measures to which may enable youths to desist from using it.

Statement of the Problem

Substance use is not a strange phenomenon, rather a global regional and national dimension as documented. The physical, psychological, social and economic consequences of the drug problems among youths are becoming more apparent, worrisome and disturbing. In particular, drug use among youth in Keffi has been on the rise in recent years, with anti-narcotics officials and experts warning of serious social consequences if the problem is not addressed (NDLEA, 2021). One of the most delicate phases is the youth period and in many cases at this stage, the initiating of drug use may occur. Youth may abuse substances due to various reasons such as lack of adequate knowledge about the harmful effects of the substances, presenting personal independence, peer pressure, satisfying the curiosity, low levels of self-confidence, inability in maintaining inter-personal communications. A number of factors are consistently found to be related to substance use among youth including the community, school environment, peer, family and personal factors (Brook et al., 2008). Some common reasons for substance use include distance from school, lack of social support from the parent or caregivers, psychological and emotional neglect (Grobler & Khatite, 2012; Ward, 2007; Westling, et al., 2008). Beyond this, broader economic difficulties experienced

by communities due to scarce resources and lack of leisure activities are further associated with problematic behaviours (Godbey 2009; Wegner et al., 2008).

Research Questions

The study answered following research questions:

- iii. What is the predictor of depression on substance use among Youths in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State-Nigeria?
- iv. What is the predictor of anxiety on Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State-Nigeria

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated for this study.

- iii. Depression will serve as a significant predictor of substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State.
- iv. Anxiety will serve as a significant predictor of Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant for several reasons, as it contributes to both theoretical knowledge and practical interventions in addressing Research on depression, anxiety on substance use is relevant in several ways including: Identifying the determinant of depression, anxiety, on substance use levels among Youth in Keffi Local Government Area, Nasarawa State, and the findings of this study will contribute towards providing evidence-based recommendations that can be used by organizations and mental health practitioners involved in the provision of support services for Youth. The intersection of depression, anxiety, and substance use disorders represents a significant public health concern. The high prevalence of comorbidity, coupled with the complex interplay between these conditions, necessitates comprehensive and integrated treatment approaches. Ongoing research is critical to further understanding the underlying mechanisms and developing

more effective interventions to improve outcomes for individuals with these co-occurring disorders.

Scope of the Study

The study on depression and anxiety as a predictor of substance use will cover the youths who are receiving treatment and rehabilitation on drug related problems at rehabilitation center in designated Keffi, Nasarawa State. The study shall also proffer professional suggestions on controls measures to ensure that substance use is reduced to the lowest minimum. This research will be a survey study where questionnaire will be used for the collection of data and the study will be restricted only to the youth in Keffi, Nasarawa

Conceptual Clarification/Literature review

This section presents the conceptual definitions of key variables in the study and critically reviews related empirical literature to provide a theoretical and research-based foundation for understanding the depression, anxiety, on substance use levels among Youth in Keffi Local Government Area, Nasarawa State

Depression and Substance Abuse

In 2018, Adole conducted a study titled "Prevalence and Correlates of Substance Abuse among Secondary School Students in Kogi State". The researchers used the Self-Medication Hypothesis as their guiding theory. They conducted a cross-sectional survey among 500 secondary school students. The findings revealed a high prevalence of substance abuse (34.5%), with a significant association between substance abuse and symptoms of anxiety and depression. The authors concluded that anxiety and depression were significant determinants of substance abuse among youths in Kogi.

In 2019, Yusuf conducted a study titled "Socioeconomic Factors and Substance Abuse among Youths with Mental Health Issues in Keffi LGA". The Social Disorganization Theory was employed in this research. The study was conducted over two years, involving a cohort of 300 youths. The findings indicated that youths from lower socioeconomic backgrounds were more likely to resort to substance abuse when dealing with anxiety and depression. The authors highlighted the importance of addressing socioeconomic disparities in interventions aimed at reducing substance abuse.

A more recent study was conducted by Abdullahi et al., in 2021, titled "Effectiveness of Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy in Reducing Substance Abuse and Mental Health Symptoms among Youths in Lafia LGA" uses The Cognitive-Behavioral Theory in conducting the research. The researchers conducted a randomized controlled trial, involving 100 youths who received CBT and a control group of 100 youths who did not. The study found that CBT was effective in reducing both substance abuse and symptoms of anxiety and depression. The authors recommended the implementation of CBT in intervention programs for youths in Lafia LGA. In 2017, a study by Muhammad et al. titled "Mental Health Issues and Substance Abuse among Adolescents in Kano LGA" explored the prevalence of mental health issues and substance abuse in this population. The study used the Stress Process Model as its theoretical framework. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 400 adolescents. The findings revealed a high prevalence of both mental health issues (anxiety and depression) and substance abuse. The authors concluded that there was a significant association between mental health issues and substance abuse, suggesting that anxiety and depression could be determinants of substance abuse.

Anxiety and Substance use

De Berardis et al., (2008) investigated an increasing body of studies indicating that alexithymia features exist not only in classic psychosomatic disorders but also in other severe and chronic somatic diseases and psychiatric disorders such as Major Depression, and other Axis I disorders such as anxiety disorders. The authors tried to elucidate the relationships between alexithymia and anxiety disorders, in order to investigate possible psychopathological and therapeutic implications.

Another study of Ames and Roitzsch (2012), patients who endorsed a greater overall number of daily anxiety, had a higher probability of experiencing cravings. The authors propose two possible hypotheses for this finding. First, individuals who experience a greater number of anxiety may experience cravings because substance use has been associated with anxiety minor life events since these individuals have used substances as a means of coping with these events in the past. This hypothesis is consistent with the tension reduction theory of substance use as proposed by Cappell and Greeley (1987). Second, an alternative hypothesis is that individuals who report experiencing a greater number of

minor anxiety may also experience cravings because they have a heightened attention to these anxiety events, thereby influencing the number of cravings they experience.

Cummings et al., (2014) addressed descriptive and developmental factors, gender differences, suicidality, assessments, and treatment-outcome research as they relate to comorbid anxiety and depression, and to their three pathways. Research indicated that comorbidity varies depending on the specific anxiety disorder: Pathway 1 describes youth with either social phobia or separation anxiety disorder and subsequent depression, Pathway 2 applies to youth with co-primary generalised anxiety disorder and depression, and Pathway 3 includes depressed youth with subsequent social phobia. Dobrea and Păsărelu (2016) conducted comprehensive systematic searches of electronic databases (PsychInfo, Cochrane, PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science) combining terms related to online social networking with social anxiety terms, and found that only recently researchers have started to investigate their relationship with mental health.

Methodology

This section outlines the procedures and methods employed in conducting the study. It explains the research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, instruments used for data collection, methods of data collection, validity and reliability of the instruments, as well as the statistical techniques used for data analysis. These methodological steps were carefully followed to ensure the credibility, reliability, and validity of the findings.

Research Design

This study adopted a survey research design, which was deemed appropriate as it enables the collection of data from a large group of respondents using standardized questionnaires. The design facilitated the examination of depression and anxiety on substance use among Youths in Keffi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State Nigeria. The survey design was suitable because the researchers sought to describe existing conditions without manipulating the variables under investigation. In this study, the independent variables social support and demographic characteristic, while depression serves as the dependent variable.

Population Sample And Sampling Technique

The population of the study comprised both male and female youths aged 18-35 years resident in Keffi for the period of study. Following the total population of three hundred and six (306) youth as registered as confirmed by the researcher in the Keffi Youth center; the sample for this study, the researcher used Raosoft sample size calculator to determine the sample of participants used out of the total population of 306 youth. The sample size calculator gives a determined sample size of 143 participants that were used for the study; this means 143 measurements/surveys were used for a confidence level of 95% that the real value is within $\pm 5\%$ of the measured/surveyed value using the formula:

Unlimited population:

$$CI = \hat{p} \pm z \times \sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{n}}$$

Finite population:

$$CI' = \hat{p} \pm z \times \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n'} \times \frac{N-n'}{N-1}}$$

Where:

z is z score = 306

\hat{p} is the population proportion = 0.05

n and **n'** are sample size = .5

N is the population size = 143

Therefore, 143 participants was selected to participate in the study. This figure constituted the research study sample.

Research Instrument

Section: A: Beck Depression Inventory – II. The Beck Depression Inventory – II is a 21 item self-report instrument developed by Beck et al., (1996). It assesses the existence and severity of symptoms of depression. It is designed for individuals aged 13 and above. Each of the 21 items corresponding to a symptom of depression is summed to give a single score for the BDI – II Total score of 0 -13 is considered minimal depression, 14 – 19 is mild depression, 20 – 28 is moderate, and 29 – 63 is severe depression. BDI – II is positively correlated with the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale with a Pearson r of 0.71, showing good agreement. The test has a high one-week test-retest reliability (Pearson r = 0.93), suggesting that it was not overly sensitive to daily variations in mood (Beck et al.,

1996). The test also has high internal consistency ($\alpha = .91$) (Beck et al., 1996). Section: B Self-Rated Anxiety Scale (SAS) developed by Zung (1971), The SAS is a 20 item self-report tool designed for measuring the level of anxiety in an individual based on the common symptoms of anxiety. Fifteen of the items express negative experience (e.g. I feel afraid for no reason at all) while five items express positive experience (e.g. I can breathe in and out easily). To respond to the items, an individual is required to indicate how much each statement applies to him/her within one or two weeks before taking the test. The SAS is measured on a Likert scale of 1- 4 which are: "a little of the time", "some of the time", "a good part of the time" and "most of the time". The items which express positive experience are scored in reverse. After scoring, the items are summed up to provide the total raw score which range from 20 - 80. The total raw score is then converted into an "Anxiety Index" Higher scores reflect a higher level of anxiety. The conversion and interpretation of the total raw score to anxiety index is given below:

For the original scale, Zung (1971) reported an internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.74 among a sample of psychiatric and non-psychiatric patients while Ramirez and Lukenbill (2008) reported an internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.80 for the SAS among a sample of adults and caregivers. For the current study, a pilot study was conducted using a sample of 40 young adults in the Keffi local government Council, Nasarawa state, to ascertain the reliability of the SAS for the study's target population. An alpha reliability coefficient of 0.69 was obtained indicating that the SAS is reliable for use in the current study. Section: C Substance Use, using the DAST which was modeled after the widely used Michigan Alcoholism Screening Test and was developed by (Selzer, 1971). Measurement properties of the DAST were initially evaluated using a clinical sample of 256 drug-alcohol-abuse clients (Skinner, 1982). The 20-item DAST has excellent internal consistency reliability (alpha) at 0.95 for total sample and 0.86 for the drug-abuse sample. Good discrimination is evident among clients classified by their reason for seeking treatment. Most clients with alcohol-related problems scored 5 or below, whereas the majority of clients with drug problems scored 6 or above on the 20-item DAST. The DAST-10 correlates very highly ($r = 0.98$) with the longer DAST-20 and has high internal consistency reliability for a brief scale (0.92 for the total sample and 0.74 for the drug-abuse sample).

Technique for Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the demographic characteristics and general responses of participants, while inferential statistics such as multiple regression and simple linear regression were used to test the research hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

This hypothesis stated that depression would have a significant predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. This hypothesis was tested using simple linear regression and the result is presented in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Summary of simple linear regression analysis showing the predictor of depression on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State

DV	Predictors	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	p
Substance Abuse	Constant	.427	.182	21.811	1, 142			
	Depression					.427	4.670	<.001

Table 4.2 shows the predictor of depression on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result shows that depression will have a significant predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State [$R = .427$ and $R^2 = .182$; $F(1, 142) = 21.811$; $p < .001$]. The result further shows through coefficient of determination [$R^2 = .182$] that depression significantly accounted for 18.2% of the total variance observed in substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result further shows through the observation of beta weight [$\beta = .427$, $t = 4.670$; $p < .001$] that depression positively predict substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. Based on this result, hypothesis one which stated that ‘depression will have a significant predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State’ was therefore accepted

Hypothesis Two

This hypothesis stated that anxiety would have a significant predictor on Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. This hypothesis was tested using simple linear regression and the result is presented in table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Summary of simple linear regression analysis showing the predictor of anxiety on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State

DV	Predictors	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	p
Substance Abuse	Constant	.497	.247	32.215	1, 142			
	Anxiety					.497	5.676	<.001

Table 4.3 shows the predictor of anxiety on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result shows that anxiety significantly predictor on substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State [$R = .497$ and $R^2 = .247$; $F(1, 142) = 5.676$; $p < .001$]. The result further shows through coefficient of determination [$R^2 = .247$] that anxiety significantly accounted for 24.7% of the total variance observed in substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. The result further shows through the observation of beta weight [$\beta = .497$, $t = 5.676$; $p < .001$] that anxiety positively predict substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State. Based on this result, hypothesis two which stated that ‘anxiety will have a significant predictor on Substance use among Youth in Keffi Local Government Nasarawa State’ was therefore accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that depression significantly predicts substance use among youths in Keffi Local Government, accounting for 18.2% of the variance in substance use behaviors. This result aligns with the study by Adole et al., (2018), which reported a significant relationship between depression and substance abuse among secondary school students in Kogi State. Similarly, Abdullahi et al., (2021) highlighted the effectiveness of interventions like CBT in addressing both depression and substance use, underscoring the interrelation between the two. These findings support Beck’s Cognitive Theory, which posits that maladaptive schemas and negative automatic thoughts associated with depression can predispose individuals to maladaptive coping strategies, including substance use. The findings suggest the need for mental health interventions focused on early identification and treatment of depression among youths to reduce substance use.

Integrating mental health services with substance use treatment programs can create a more comprehensive support system for vulnerable youths.

The results of the second also showed that anxiety significantly predicts substance use, explaining 24.7% of the variance. This corroborates the findings of Ames and Roitzsch (2012), who observed that anxiety significantly increases cravings for substances as a coping mechanism, consistent with the tension reduction theory. Furthermore, the work of De Berardis et al., (2008) underscores the overlap between anxiety disorders and substance use, suggesting that the physiological arousal associated with anxiety often drives self-medication behaviors. These results align with Freud's Psychoanalytic Theory, which postulates that anxiety acts as a defense mechanism, potentially leading to maladaptive behaviors such as substance use to manage unconscious conflicts. The significant role of anxiety in substance use underscores the importance of anxiety management in prevention and treatment strategies. Programs designed to teach stress-reduction techniques, such as mindfulness or cognitive-behavioral approaches, could effectively reduce substance use by addressing anxiety triggers.

Lastly, the study found a significant gender difference in substance use, with females reporting higher mean scores compared to males. This finding contrasts with earlier studies such as those by Kandel et al., (1978) and Wilsnack et al., (1984), which identified males as more likely to engage in substance use. However, the results align with more recent research by Greenfield et al., (2010), which suggests that females may experience more severe consequences from substance use and are more likely to use substances as a response to psychological distress. The Gender and Trauma Theory by Pedersen et al., (2017) may provide insight, highlighting how societal pressures and trauma differently influence substance use patterns across genders. These findings indicate the need for gender-specific interventions in addressing substance use. Female-targeted programs should consider addressing underlying psychological distress and societal pressures, while male-focused interventions might emphasize peer influence and social norms. Tailored interventions can enhance the effectiveness of prevention and treatment strategies.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there is a significant association between symptoms of depression , anxiety and substance use among youths in Keffi LGA. This relationship is often reciprocal, with psychological distress potentially leading to substance use as a maladaptive coping mechanism (self-medication), and substance use, in turn, exacerbating mental health symptoms. A substantial number of youths engaging in substance use also exhibit elevated levels of depression and anxiety, highlighting a critical issue of co-occurring mental health and substance use disorders (dual diagnosis).Risk Factors: Factors such as peer pressure and male gender were also likely identified as significant predictors of substance use, consistent with regional findings, which may further complicate the mental health-substance use link.

Recommendations

The study's findings necessitate a multi-level approach involving clinical, educational, and community interventions.

- iv. Integrated Treatment Services: Clinical psychology services (mental health and substance use) should be integrated, shifting away from treating these conditions in isolation.
- v. School-Based Mental Health Programs: Implement Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)-based counseling and psycho-education programs in secondary schools and tertiary institutions within Keffi LGA. These programs should aim to teach youths:
- vi. Community and Family Intervention: Public health campaigns should target parents and community leaders to raise awareness about the signs of depression, anxiety, and substance use in youths.

Implications for Clinical Psychology

The study's results have several significant implications for the practice and development of clinical psychology services in Keffi and similar settings in Nigeria.

- iv. Focus on Assessment and Early Detection: Clinicians must routinely screen all youth presenting with substance use problems for co-occurring depression and anxiety, and vice-

versa, to ensure comprehensive diagnosis. This requires using culturally sensitive and validated assessment tools.

- v. **Specialized Training:** There is an urgent need for mental health professionals to receive specialized training in co-morbidity treatment models like Motivational Interviewing (MI) and integrated CBT for substance use and anxiety/depression.
- vi. **Advocacy and Policy:** The findings provide empirical evidence to advocate for increased funding and resource allocation from the Keffi LGA and Nasarawa State government for youth mental health and substance abuse services, including the deployment of more career masters and psychologists in schools, as current efforts may be insufficient.

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